

Mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals. Part-XV. Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde or 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde

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Abstract : Reactions of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} chlorides with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde or 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have yielded mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II}; HL = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and HL' = 2-hydroxybenzophenone, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde or 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, TLC, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, alkaline metal ions, IR spectra, NMR spectra.

The alkaline earth metal complexes of the type ML₂ have been widely studied. β-Diketonate complexes of these metals have been synthesized and the structures of Mg(pentane-2,4-dionato)₂(H₂O)₂, Mg(1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dionato)₂(DMF)₂ and Ca(1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dionato)₂(EtOH)_{1/2} have been reported^{1,2}. Fenton³ has isolated mixed ligand complexes of the type ML₂L'. Mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} with salicylaldehyde, 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone and β-diketones such as acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane have been reported earlier from our laboratories⁴. In the present paper the mixed ligand complexes of the type [MLL'(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II}; HL=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (hnpH); HL' = 2-hydroxybenzophenone (hbpH), 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (5-BrsalH) or 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-ClSalH) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of the metal ions with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde or 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (Schemes 1 and 2).

The resulting mixed ligand complexes are yellow solids. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and n-hexane but are soluble in DMF and DMSO. Most of them decompose on heating at higher temperatures and some of them decomposed within a few days. The molar conductances of the complexes are very low

Scheme 2

indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Presence of two coordinated water molecules in the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals with similar ligands has been established by TGA studies⁵. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The metal atom appears to be hexa-coordinated in these complexes and the probable geometry may be octahedral⁶.

TLC of all the mixed ligand complexes and the corresponding bis-complexes was performed on silica gel G using a benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1, v/v) mixture as the solvent. Spots on the TLC plates were detected by iodine vapours. Mixed ligand complexes show a single spot with R_f values being the intermediate of the two corresponding bis-complexes. This indicates that they are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two bis-complexes.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals

Compd.	Colour and Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
			Metal	C	H
[Mg(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 200	64	5.59 (5.67)	67.21 (67.24)	4.68 (4.70)
[Mg(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 215	70	6.19 (6.28)	58.82 (58.85)	3.86 (3.90)
[Mg(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 230	45	5.55 (5.63)	50.01 (50.10)	3.46 (3.50)
[Ca(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 220	62	9.02 (9.00)	64.84 (64.86)	4.52 (4.54)
[Ca(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 210	71	10.10 (9.93)	53.54 (53.67)	3.72 (3.75)
[Ca(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 215	57	8.86 (8.94)	48.30 (48.34)	3.33 (3.38)
[Sr(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 190	62	17.94 (17.81)	58.62 (58.58)	4.07 (4.10)
[Sr(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 225	64	19.58 (19.45)	47.97 (48.00)	3.31 (3.36)
[Sr(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 245	39	17.94 (17.71)	43.59 (43.69)	3.01 (3.05)
[Ba(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 215	54	25.12 (25.35)	53.21 (53.21)	3.69 (3.72)
[Ba(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 225	65	27.23 (27.46)	43.20 (43.23)	3.01 (3.02)
[Ba(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow 235	76	24.95 (25.22)	38.79 (39.70)	2.70 (2.78)

Infrared spectra

Important bands in the IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals are recorded in Table 2. The $\nu_{C=O}$ frequencies are observed at 1630–1640 cm^{-1} . In free 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone bands at 1650, 1670, 1680 and 1640 cm^{-1} respectively are observed due to $\nu_{C=O}$.⁷ Thus these bands shift to lower wave number side in the complexes supporting the coordination of these ligands to the metal ions. Such shifts to lower wave number side on complexation have been reported in the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth and transition metals^{8–10}. In the mixed ligand complexes, the weak bands in the region 400–550 cm^{-1} which are absent in the free ligands, may be assigned to ν_{M-O} vibrations¹¹.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra

¹H NMR spectra of few representative mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals were recorded in

DMSO-*d*₆ and the δ values (ppm) of the peaks of various protons are given in Table 3. In free 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde the aldehydic CH proton gives a singlet at δ 10.53 and 10.30 ppm respectively which is shifted upfield in the mixed ligand complexes $[M(5\text{-Brsal})(\text{hnp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where M = Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba) and appears at δ 10.15–10.45 and 9.65–9.85 ppm respectively. This upfield shift of CH proton peaks supports the coordination of the C=O group of these ligand moieties to the metal atom. In free 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde the OH proton peak appears at δ 13.15 and 10.88 ppm respectively. This peak disappears in the mixed ligand complexes of these ligands indicating the formation of Mg-O bond with the phenolic oxygen of these ligands through replacement of hydrogen of the OH group. The peaks due to aromatic protons of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde moieties appear as multiplets in the region δ 6.38–7.65 ppm. Thus the NMR spectra confirm the proposed structures of the mixed ligand complexes.

Table 2. Absorption bands (cm^{-1}) in the IR spectra of mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals^a

Compd	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{M-O}
[Mg(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1645s	410w, 460w, 475w, 500m
[Mg(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1640vs	410w, 420w, 450w, 500m
[Mg(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1630s	405w, 475w, 520m, 550m
[Ca(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1630vs	420w, 440w, 460w, 500m
[Ca(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1640vs	420w, 450w, 500m
[Ca(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1640vs	420w, 450w, 480w
[Sr(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1640vs	410w, 425w, 460w, 490w
[Sr(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1620vs	440w, 420w, 460w, 480w, 520w
[Sr(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1640vs	410w, 420w, 440w, 460w, 480w, 520m
[Ba(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1630s	410w, 420w, 440w, 460w, 520m
[Ba(hnp)(5-Clisal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1620vs	410w, 420w, 450w, 460w, 480w, 520m
[Ba(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1650vs	410w, 420w, 450w, 480w, 520m

^as = strong, vs = very strong, m = medium, w = weak

Table 3. Chemical shifts (δ , ppm) in the ¹H NMR spectra of mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals

Compd	δ (ppm)		Aromatic protons
	Aldehydic proton		
	Brsal	hnp	
[Mg(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	9.65(s)	10.15(s)	6.38–7.28(m)
[Ca(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	9.80(s)	10.42(s)	6.62–7.65(m)
[Sr(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	9.85(s)	10.45(s)	6.65–7.55(m)
[Ba(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	9.86(s)	10.45(s)	6.66–7.58(m)

s = singlet, m = multiplet

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka), 2-hydroxybenzophenone (Aldrich), 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich), 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich) and ethanol were purified by distillation. $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Merck) were of A R. grade.

Analytical methods : Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically by EDTA and barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as a reference on a Bruker 300 NMR spectrometer.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic solution of metal chloride (2.90 mmol, 0.5929 g in 4 ml ethanol) an ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (2.90 mmol, 0.5022 g in 2 ml of ethanol) and 2-hydroxybenzophenone (2.90 mmol, 0.5754 g in 2 ml of ethanol) were added. The pH of the resulting solution was raised to 7 by adding 2% NaOH solution (~ 2 ml) dropwise with constant stirring. After stirring for 3–4 h the resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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